

CAREER RELATED ISSUES OF WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN SELECT HOSPITALS OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract:

The women perform many functions in society and for the society. They produce children, they are mother and wives. However, they are largely excluded from high status occupations and positions of power. They do cooking mending, sewing, washing and many other odd jobs. But in terms of the rewards of prestige, wealth and power, women invariably come off worse. The problems of working women are multidimensional and differ from women to women. The present study is an attempt to portray the career related issues of women employees in select hospitals {GEMS, KIMS, RIMS & GMR} of Andhra Pradesh.

Keywords: Andhra Pradesh, Career, Employees, Hospitals, Women

I. Introduction

Health care plays an important part in our lives; it affects the way the hospitals live together and the expectations. The hospitals have for our standard of living. The delivery of health services to the community is highly visible and open to criticism. Being the most valuable public service in the world helping communities to enjoy long and healthy lives, there is nothing more rewarding than contributing to its success. Nursing tasks are considered to be significant ones. There is no doubt that the nursing staff really contribute to the patient care process meaningfully. However, the nursing staffs do many jobs which are not specific to their profession. In such cases it may affect the quality of nursing specific work as well decrease the intensity level of their work. Also there is a scope for developing the perception a low value is assigned to the nursing profession. Every nurse can choose to do the job that

challenges, is interesting and makes her feel proud. If the staff have an opportunity to do such kind of jobs the women employee is motivated, satisfied and achieves a good performance. Theoretically speaking the workplace where the employees perform high complexity tasks shows that there is very low absenteeism Turner and Lawrence identify five job characteristics and their relationship to personal and work outcomes. According to the experience and practice of the staff members on the job activities may rate each characteristic high or low.

Purpose of the study: The purpose of the study is to know the working women issues in various aspects and how it is related to their career and personal life.

Data Collection Methods: The entire study is based on primary data and the researchers have used a structured questionnaire to collect the first hand information from 340 respondents. The second hand

data has been gathered from journals and websites etc.

Statistical Tools: The collected data has been analyzed by using tabulation and percentage analysis methods.

S. No	Opinion	Public				Private				Total	
		GEMS		KIMS		RIMS		GMR			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	Strongly Disagree	0	3	0	2	0	3	0	2	1	2.9
		2	3	1	0	5	3	2	5	0	4
2.	Disagree	0	3	0	2	0	3	0	2	1	2.9
		2	3	1	0	5	3	2	5	0	4
3.	Neutral	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	4	11.7
		6	0	6	0	7	3	1	8	0	6
4.	Agree	4	7	3	7	1	7	6	7	2	76.4
		7	8	8	0	5	7	0	0	6	4
5.	Strongly Agree	0	5	0	8	0	5	0	6	2	5.8
		3	0	4	0	8	3	5	3	0	8
	Total	6	10	5	10	15	10	8	10	34	100
		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Employees are clear what is expected at work

From the above Table 1 designs about the employee is clear what is expected at work shown the results of four hospitals are GEMS, KIMS, RIMS and GMR. In the four hospitals strongly Disagree are 2.94%, Disagree are 2.94%, Neutral are 11.76%, Agree are 76.47%, Strongly Agree are 5.88%. In GEMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 5%, Agree are 78.3%, Neutral are 10%, Disagree are 3.3% and strongly Disagree are 3.3%. In KIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 8%, Agree are 76%, Neutral are 12%,

Disagree are 2%, and Strongly Disagree are 2%. In RIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 5.3%, Agree are 76.7%, Neutral are 11.3%, Disagree are 3.3% and strongly Disagree are 3.3%. In GMR the respondents Strongly Agree are 6.3%, Agree are 75%, Neutral are 13.8%, Disagree are 2.5% and strongly Disagree are 2.5%.The employee can decided when to take a break

S. No	Opinion	Public				Private				Total	
		GEMS		KIMS		RIMS		GMR			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2.	Disagree	1	1	0	1	2	1	1	1	6	17.6
		1	8	3	0	7	0	4	5	0	4
3.	Neutral	0	8	0	8	1	8	0	1	3	8.8
		5	3	4	0	3	7	8	0	0	2
4.	Agree	4	7	3	7	1	7	5	6	2	70.5
		3	1	6	0	6	7	5	8	0	8
5.	Strongly Agree	0	1	2	4	0	2	0	3	1	2.9
		1	7	0	0	4	7	3	8	0	4
	Total	6	10	5	10	15	10	8	10	34	100
		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 2 Employee can decide when to take a break

The above Table designs about the employee can decided when to take a break shown the results of four hospitals are GEMS, KIMS, RIMS, and GMR. In the four hospitals strongly Disagree are nil, Disagree are 17.64%, Neutral are 8.82%, Agree are 70.58%, Strongly Agree are 2.94%. In GEMS the

respondents Strongly Agree are 1.7%, Agree are 71.7%, Neutral are 8.3%, Disagree are 18.3% and strongly Disagree are nil. In KIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 4%, Agree are 72%, Neutral are 8%, Disagree are 16%, and Strongly Disagree are nil. In RIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 2.7%, Agree are 70.7%, Neutral are 8.7%, Disagree are 18% and strongly Disagree are nil. In GMR the respondents Strongly Agree are 3.8%, Agree are 68.8%, Neutral are 10%, Disagree are 17.5% and strongly Disagree are nil.

Table 3 Employees know how to get their job done

S. No.	Opinion	Public				Private				Total		
		GEMS		KIMS		RIMS		GMR				
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
1.	Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	3	0.88
2.	Disagree	0	3	0	2	0	2	0	2	0	7	2.05
3.	Neutral	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	11.76
4.	Agree	4	7	3	7	1	7	5	7	2	7	73.52
5.	Strongly Agree	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	11.76
	Total	6	10	5	10	15	10	8	10	34	10	

The above table designs about the employee know how about getting the job done shown the results of four hospitals are GEMS, KIMS, RIMS, GMR. In the four hospitals strongly Disagree are 0.88%, Disagree are 2.05%, Neutral are 11.76%, Agree are 73.52%, Strongly Agree are 11.76%. In GEMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 10%, Agree are 76.7%, Neutral are 10%, Disagree are 3.3% and strongly Disagree are nil. In KIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 14%, Agree are 72%, Neutral are 12%, Disagree are 2%, and Strongly Disagree are nil. In RIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 11.3%, Agree with 74%, Neutral are 11.3%, Disagree are 1.33% and Strongly Disagree are 2%. In GMR the respondents Strongly Agree are 12.5%, Agree are 71.3%, Neutral are 13.8%, Disagree are 2.5% and strongly Disagree are nil.

Table 4 Employee is subject to personal harassment inform of unkind words or behavior

Table 4 postulates about The employee is subject to personal harassment inform of unkind words or behaviour shown the results of four hospitals are GEMS, KIMS, RIMS, GMR. In the four hospitals strongly Disagree are 8.82%, Disagree are 35.29%, Neutral are 11.76%, Agree are 41.17%, Strongly Agree are 2.94%. In GEMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 3.3%, Agree are 45%, Neutral are 10%, Disagree are 31.7% and strongly Disagree are 10. In KIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 2%, Agree are 40%, Neutral are 12%, Disagree are 38%, and Strongly Disagree are 8%. In RIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 3.3%, Agree are 42%, Neutral are 11.3%, Disagree are 34% and strongly Disagree are 9.3%. In GMR the respondents Strongly Agree are 2.5%, Agree are 37.5%, Neutral are 13.8%, Disagree are 38.8% and strongly Disagree are 7.5%.

S. No.	Opinion	Public				Private				Total	
		GEMS		KIMS		RIMS		GMR			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%

1.	Strongly Disagree	06	10	4	80	14	93	06	75	30	82
2.	Disagree	19	31	19	38	51	34	31	38	12	35
3.	Neutral	06	10	6	12	17	11	11	13	40	17
4.	Agree	27	45	20	40	63	42	30	37	14	41
5.	Strongly Agree	02	33	01	20	05	33	02	25	10	29
	Total	60	100	50	100	150	100	80	100	340	100

Table 5 Employees have unachievable deadlines

Table 5 explicit about the employee has unachievable deadlines shown the results of four hospitals are GEMS, KIMS, RIMS, and GMR. In the four hospitals strongly Disagree are 2.94%, Disagree are 29.41%, Neutral are 17.64%, Agree are 27.35%, Strongly Agree are 22.64%. In GEMS the respondents are Strongly Agree are 28.33%, Agree are 26.77%, Neutral are 16.7%, Disagree are 26.7% and Strongly Disagree are 1.7%. In KIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 12%, Agree are 34%, Neutral are 18%, Disagree are 32%, and Strongly Disagree are 4%. In RIMS the respondents are Strongly Agree are 24.67%, Agree are 26.67%, Neutral are 17.3%, Disagree are 28.7% and Strongly Disagree are 2.7%. In GMR the respondents are

Strongly Agree are 24.67%, Agree are 26.67%, Neutral are 18.8%, Disagree are 31.3% and Strongly Disagree are 3.8%.

Table 6 Employee had given supportive feedback on work they do.

Table 6 examines about the employee had given supportive feedback shown the results of four hospitals are GEMS, KIMS, RIMS, GMR. In the four hospitals strongly Disagree are 2.94%, Disagree are 2.94%, Neutral are 22.94%, Agree are 52.94%, Strongly Agree are 18.23%. In GEMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 5%, Agree are 51.7%, Neutral are 38.3%, Disagree are 1.7% and Strongly Disagree are 3.3%. In KIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 8%, Agree are 52%, Neutral are 34%, Disagree are 4%, and Strongly Disagree are 2%. In RIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 33.33%, Agree are 54%, Neutral are 6.63%, Disagree are 2.7% and strongly Disagree are 3.3%. In GMR the respondents Strongly Agree are 6.3%, Agree are 52.5%, Neutral are 35%, Disagree are 3.8% and strongly Disagree are 2.5%.

Table 7 Employees have to work intensively?

Table 7 examines about The employee had to work intensively shown the results of four hospitals are GEMS, KIMS, RIMS, GMR. In the four hospitals strongly Disagree are 10.88%, Disagree are 12.05%, Neutral are 7.64%, Agree are 47.35%, Strongly Agree are 22.05%. In GEMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 16.67%, Agree are 56.67%, Neutral are 10%, Disagree are 8.33% and strongly Disagree are 8.33%. In KIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 20%, Agree with 40%, Neutral are 10%, Disagree are 12%, and Strongly Disagree are 18%. In RIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 22%, Agree are 53.33%, Neutral are 4.67%, Disagree are 3.33% and Strongly Disagree are 6.67%. In GMR the respondents Strongly Agree are 27.5%, Agree are 33.75%, Neutral are 10%, Disagree are 12.5% and strongly Disagree are 16.25.

Table 8 Employee have a stay in their own work speed

The above table spells about the employee had own work speed shown the results of four hospitals are GEMS, KIMS, RIMS and GMR. In the four

S. No.	Opinion	Public				Private				Total	
		GEMS		KIMS		RIMS		GMR			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	Strongly Disagree	5	83.3	9	118	10	67	13	165	37	108
2.	Disagree	5	83.3	6	122	20	33	10	125	41	120
3.	Neutral	6	10	5	107	47	67	8	10	26	74
4.	Agree	34	567	20	400	80	33	27	375	161	473
5.	Strongly Agree	10	167	10	200	33	22	22	275	75	220
	Total	60	100	50	100	105	100	80	100	340	100

2.94%, Neutral are 20.58%, Agree are 68.82%, Strongly Agree are 8.82%. In GEMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 6.7%, Agree are 71.7%, Neutral are 18.3%, Disagree are 3.3% and Strongly Disagree are nil.

In KIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 12%, Agree are 66%, Neutral are 20%, Disagree are 2%, and Strongly Disagree are nil. In RIMS the respondents Strongly Agree are 8%, Agree are 68.7%, Neutral are 20%, Disagree are 3.3% and strongly Disagree are nil. In GMR the respondents Strongly Agree are 10%, Agree are 63.7%, Neutral are 23.8%, Disagree are 2.5% and strongly Disagree are nil.

Conclusion:

The opportunities for career advancement for nurses are significantly lesser in government as well as private sector. This is a major challenge for nurses to achieve reputed positions in health care system. Family time was interrupted because of shift-work, the inability to disconnect from work responsibilities, worrying about the completion and accuracy of delivered patient care while at home, work-related conversations, and time-constraints in both domains. Nurses missed events with family because of work schedules that did not fit with family schedules. Missing family events created disappointment about the nurses' choice in workplace and the workplace requirements.

hospitals strongly Disagree are nil, Disagree are

S. No.	Opinion	Public				Private				Total	
		GEMS		KIMS		RIMS		GMR			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	Strongly Disagree	2	33	1	20	5	33	2	25	10	24
2.	Disagree	1	17	2	40	4	27	3	38	10	29
3.	Neutral	2	33	1	40	1	6.6	2	28	7	29
4.	Agree	3	51	2	50	8	54	4	55	18	54
5.	Strongly Agree	3	50	4	80	5	33	5	63	6	23
	Total	6	100	5	100	15	100	8	100	34	100

S. No.	Opinion	Public				Private				Total	
		GEMS		KIMS		RIMS		GMR			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2.	Disagree	0	33	0	20	0	0	0	25	1	9
3.	Neutral	1	18	1	20	3	30	1	13	7	25
4.	Agree	4	71	3	60	10	63	5	63	23	68

			7		0				7		2
5.	Strongly Agree	0	67	0	0	1	12	8	0	1	38
	Total	6	100	5	100	15	150	10	80	10	34

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